

Another proof to the formula of the permutations of a multiset applying mathematical induction

Leonidas Aslanidis
email: leonaslanithis@hotmail.gr

University of Patras, School of mathematics

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Abstract

In this short paper we demonstrate a new proof to the following problem: Suppose a finite multiset $\{a_1 \cdot m, a_2 \cdot m, \dots, a_n \cdot m\}$, then the total permutations of this multiset are $\frac{(nm)!}{(m!)^n}$. The proof is based on the mathematical induction.

1 Demonstration of the proof

In order to enumerate the permutations of this multiset $\{a_1 \cdot m, a_2 \cdot m, \dots, a_n \cdot m\}$ we need the following lemma:

Lemma. *The proposition $\binom{(k+1)m}{m} = (k+1)\binom{(k+1)m-1}{m-1}$ is valid.*

Proof. Easy exercise □

Proposition. *Suppose a finite multiset $\{a_1 \cdot m, a_2 \cdot m, \dots, a_n \cdot m\}$, then the total permutations of this multiset are $\frac{(nm)!}{(m!)^n}$.*

Proof. It will be constructed with induction. Suppose a multiset $\{a_1 \cdot m\}$, It is obvious that this multiset has one permutation. Therefore, for $n = 1$ the proposition is valid ($1 = \frac{(1m)!}{(m!)^1}$). Suppose that it is also valid for $n = k$, that is, that the permutations of the following multiset: $\{a_1 \cdot m, a_2 \cdot m, \dots, a_k \cdot m\}$ are $\frac{(km)!}{(m!)^k}$ (inductive supposition). We need to prove the same for $n = k + 1$, that is, that the permutations of the following multiset: $\{a_1 \cdot m, a_2 \cdot m, \dots, a_{k+1} \cdot m\}$ are $\frac{((k+1)m)!}{(m!)^{k+1}}$. Suppose a tuple with $(k+1) \cdot m$ objects. Without loss of generality we choose the first place of this $(k+1) \cdot m$ -tuple. We have $k+1$ choices for placing a specific object in the first place of the tuple. We can either choose the a_1 object, or the a_2 object, or... the a_{k+1} object. If we choose the a_i ($i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k+1\}$) object for the first place, then $(m-1) \cdot a_i$ objects remain to be placed in the rest

$(k+1) \cdot m - 1$ places of the tuple. Those $m - 1$ objects can be placed in the rest places in $\binom{(k+1)m-1}{m-1}$ ways. Therefore the total combinations of selecting an object for the first place, and positioning the remaining similar $(m - 1)$ objects in the remaining $(k+1) \cdot m - 1$ places of the tuple are $\binom{(k+1)m-1}{m-1} (k+1) = \binom{(k+1)m}{m}$ (see lemma above). For each and every one of these $\binom{(k+1)m-1}{m-1} (k+1)$ combinations the rest objects can be placed on the remaining $k \cdot m$ places of the tuple in $\frac{(km)!}{(m!)^k}$ (inductive supposition). Therefore the total permutations of this multiset are $\binom{(k+1)m}{m} \frac{(km)!}{(m!)^k} = \binom{(k+1)m}{m} \binom{(k-1)m}{m} \dots \binom{2m}{m} \binom{m}{m} = \frac{((k+1)m)!}{(m!)^{k+1}}$. The proposition is now proven using mathematical induction. \square

References

- [1] Aslanidis, L. (2023, September 12). Two alternative proofs to an equivalent problem of the permutations of a multiset applying mathematical induction. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/jgb57>